

THE ROLE OF MORAL CORRECTION OF CONVICTED PERSONS IN THE EXPERIENCE OF ADVANCED FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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In recent years, a number of measures have been taken to improve the penitentiary system. In particular, comprehensive measures were implemented to involve convicts in productive labor and unconditionally observe their labor rights, respect their honor and dignity, eliminate corruption and abuse of official authority in this area, and strengthen the material and technical base of penitentiary institutions.

The activities of educational institutions in the penitentiary system have been fundamentally reformed. Innovative pedagogical technologies have been introduced into the process of educating convicts, and, first and foremost, mechanisms for vocational training of minors and convicts without professional skills have been revised.

The efforts to involve convicts in useful labor should not contradict international practices. Specifically, Rule 96, Part 1 of the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners (Mandela Rules) states that prisoners must be given the opportunity to work or be employed if they are found to be physically and mentally fit by a doctor or other qualified medical professional.[1]

According to Article 88 of the current Criminal Executive Code, the main purpose of involving convicts in labor is to cultivate in them a need to engage in socially useful activities. Persons sentenced to deprivation of liberty should work, taking into account their gender, age, health status, ability to work and, if possible, specialization. The labor relations of convicts are regulated by labor legislation, taking into account the exceptions and restrictions provided for in the Criminal Executive Code.[2]

Additionally, this article stipulates that men over sixty years old, women over fifty-five years old, and persons with disabilities of groups I and II are involved in labor at their own discretion. Convicted women are granted leave from work for pregnancy and childbirth for a period established by law.

Rule 96, Part 1 of the Mandela Rules states that "prisoners should be assigned sufficient useful work to occupy them for a normal working day."

In our opinion, this rule is intended to ensure that working hours are observed when engaging prisoners in labor. For this reason, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-683 dated April 21, 2021 "On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan" amended Part 6 of Article 88 of the Criminal Procedure Code. The amendment stipulates that the labor of prisoners is prohibited in jobs forbidden by labor legislation, and the use of female and juvenile prisoners' labor is not allowed in such work.[4] The amendment stated that the labor of convicts is not allowed to use the labor of women and juvenile convicts in work prohibited by labor legislation.[4]

While Rule 97, Part 1 of the Mandela Rules states that the work of prisoners should not be afflictive, Article 88 of the current Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan specifies that the list of jobs and positions prohibited for prisoners is determined by legislation. Prisoners are required to perform assigned work honestly and conscientiously, comply with labor and technological discipline, technical safety rules, and labor protection requirements. Prisoners are prohibited from stopping their assigned work to resolve labor and other disputes.

Part 2 of Rule 97 of the Mandela Rules states that prisoners should not be held in slavery or servitude.[5] However, contrary to this rule, Article 13 of the U.S. Constitution, adopted in Philadelphia on September 17, 1787, states that U.S. citizens shall not be subject to involuntary servitude or slavery, except as punishment for crime.

This implies that Article 13 of the U.S. Constitution allows for the enslavement of prisoners. This indicates that the rights of prisoners in the United States are being violated. Furthermore, the United States has allowed private entrepreneurs to privatize correctional institutions. This experiment was reflected in the first privately built and operated correctional facility (San Quentin State Prison) opened in California in the 1850s.

However, this experiment was unsuccessful - scandals surrounding corruption and mismanagement forced the state government to refuse to contract with the private company and to return the management of the institution to its own control.[6] But this experiment was unsuccessful - scandals surrounding corruption and mismanagement, forced the state government to refuse to enter into a contract with a private company, and sentencing to return management of the institution to its own hands.[6]

In our opinion, this practice is entirely inappropriate, as the primary goal of penal institutions is not to generate profit, but to morally rehabilitate convicts. Since the beginning of the 20th century, all correctional services in the United States have been provided solely in institutions built and funded by the state from the state budget (federal or state). In numerous cases, non-governmental non-profit organizations and volunteer citizens provide various rehabilitation services for inmates. The cost of maintaining correctional institutions has traditionally been high, so the practice of contracting with private companies to provide a range of services (typically medical services, food, and transportation) is widespread.[7]

Additionally, in the USA, labor contracts have been established with state and private contractors for the employment of inmates by correctional institutions and the utilization of their labor. By 1885, in

13 states of the United States, correctional institutions had concluded contracts with private entrepreneurs to engage inmates in labor and use their work. The labor of inmates was economically beneficial both for the contractors and for the administration of the correctional facility. Income did not always cover the costs of maintaining prisoners, but through this method, the administration of the penal system brought the institutions to a level of self-sufficiency, and there were even instances where a portion of the funds received for financing was returned to the state budget.[8]

In our view, during this period, the United States implemented the initial stages of public-private partnership agreements, but it would be accurate to say that the purpose of engaging inmates in work was not moral rehabilitation, but rather economic development.[9]

Currently, the form of private penitentiary institutions is still quite popular in the United States. GEO Group, one of the largest commercial private prison operators in the United States, reported revenue of \$2.26 billion for the first month of 2022, and an annual net income of \$159.2 million for 2021, which amounts to \$1.32 per shareholder.[10]

The company's net income and earnings from shares increased significantly compared to 2020 (up from \$113 million), although two of its agency contracts expired in November and were not extended by the U.S. Federal Bureau of Prisons.[11] How can these organizations engage in mutual relations without an existing contract? How can these organizations interact without a contract?

The world's largest private prison operator, CoreCivic, signed a new three-year contract with the State of New Mexico in September 2021 to lease the 596-bed Northwest New Mexico Correctional Center.[12]

Statistics show that currently in the country's prisons more than 2 million people are being held, which has increased by 500 percent over the past 40 years.

This accounts for a quarter of all prisoners in the world.[13] In 2019, 115,428 people were held in private prisons in the United States, which represents 8% of the total number of inmates held in the United States. Since 2000, the number of people held in private prisons has increased by 32%.[14]

Today, private prisons in the United States are heavily criticized for staff shortages, drug abuse, forced labor, and lack of medical care.

The experience of the United States shows that the practices in the country's penal system contradict Rule 97, Part 2 of the Mandela Rules, which states that prisoners should not be held in slavery or under coercion.[15]

Also, in this experience, it is evident that the country itself has not adhered to regulatory legal acts regarding private contractors who have operated normally during the past year, despite the decree signed by US President Joseph Biden on March 17, 2021, aimed at canceling federal contracts with private prisons in order to abandon this practice.

On January 26, 2021, J. Biden signed a decree to reform the country's penitentiary system

and ultimately abolish private prisons,[16] but this decree was not implemented in practice.

In our opinion, convicts can be subjected to slavery in the United States, as we have already seen, and the country's constitution permits this. Serving a sentence in private penal institutions is also considered a form of slavery.

Since gaining independence, there has never been any mention of involving convicts or citizens in slavery within the framework of our country's adopted constitution and laws. As evidence of this, our legislation states that persons sentenced to deprivation of liberty are usually employed in penal institutions and enterprises of their organizations, and in some cases, in other enterprises, provided that necessary protection and complete separation are ensured. Convicts are not allowed to work for private individuals.[17]

Now let's examine the experience of China in employing convicts and utilizing their labor. This country has a unique approach to involving convicts in work. The main part of the profit from finished goods sold in China is allocated

to the educational process organized for convicts, the development of the colony, and the payment for production purchases. The fact is that in Chinese penal institutions, prisoners are not paid for their work. The provision of all necessary items for living in penitentiary institutions, including clothing, food, and essential services, is considered full provision at the expense of the state. The working hours of convicts are 12 hours a day. The majority (up to 80%) of the products made by convicts are exported.[18] In our opinion, it is necessary to pay attention to this best practice. In our opinion, it is necessary to pay attention to this best practice.

At this point, a question arises: what is the volume of products produced in our country's penitentiary institutions today through the socially useful work of convicts? Unfortunately, currently, products manufactured by penitentiary institutions are not exported to other countries.

From this perspective, it is necessary to organize the export of products manufactured as a result of engaging prisoners in productive labor in penitentiary institutions. The following actions need to be taken:

First, to bring the goods produced by prisoners' labor in penitentiary institutions to export quality, it is essential to update the material and technical base of penal institutions and re-equip the facilities for manufacturing goods that meet international standards;

Second, it is necessary to create electronic platforms and telegram bots for online trading by penitentiary institutions.

Prisoners who are not engaged in work are not granted annual paid leave. According to Article 70 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation, the prison administration may involve prisoners in unpaid maintenance work for no more than 4 hours a week. Deductions from wages and other income of convicts sentenced to imprisonment can only be made from their wages, pensions, and other income in accordance with part four of Article 99 of this Criminal Code (Prisoners receiving wages and pensions cover the costs of food, clothing, utilities,

and personal hygiene products, except for special meals and special clothing. For prisoners who evade work, these expenses are deducted from the funds available in their personal accounts. Reimbursement of the cost of food, clothing, household services, and personal hygiene products is carried out monthly within the framework of actual expenses incurred in a given month).

This foreign practice is reflected in the current Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the republic's regulatory legal acts. Unlike in Russia,

in Uzbekistan's practice of employing prisoners, labor leave is provided only in settlement colonies. This practice is not implemented in other types of penitentiary institutions.

In accordance with Article 91 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, prisoners in settlement colonies have the right to annual paid leave of fifteen working days. Leave is granted with the right to leave the settlement colony territory in the manner prescribed by Article 82 of this Criminal Code. The time spent by a prisoner in the disciplinary unit of the penal colony is not included in the period required for granting paid annual leave.

We can see that in the Russian Federation, a calendar day practice is used when providing labor leave to prisoners, while in our legislation, a 15-day practice is established. Additionally, the penitentiary system of the Russian Federation does not specify which category of prisoners serving sentences in which type of colony are eligible for leave. In our system, this category is established, and leave is only allowed for those in settlement colonies.

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